

UZBEK WOMAN HEADED THE SUPREME COURT FOR THE FIRST TIME IN THE WORLD

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Annotation: This article provides information about the life and activities of Khadicha Sulaymanova, an academician, scientist, one of the first female lawyers in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Andijan, Russian school, criminal court proceedings, Minister of Justice, Supreme Court Judge, Tashkent Scientific Research Institute of Judicial Expertise, criminal law.

Khadicha Sulaymanova was born on June 3, 1913 in Andijan. Hearing stories from his mother about what kind of person his father was, he intends to learn many languages like his father. At that time, the situation in Uzbek land was complicated. In 1926, the "Hujum" company was started to remove the veil from women. On the one hand, there are those who oppose it. In 1928, there are reports that 203 women who threw away the veil, participated in the eradication of illiteracy or participated in artistic amateur circles were killed. Nevertheless, the issue of women's rights did not fall from the agenda, on the contrary, it became stronger. Khadija, who has been reading all this, understands that she can achieve success only by gaining knowledge. In 1929, an open trial was held in Margilon regarding the murder of Nurkhan. People from many parts of the Fergana Valley take part in the trial. Seventeen-year-old Khadicha Sulaymanova was among them. He was interested in how the defendants were tried. Khadicha, who was affected by the speech of Tajikhon Shodiyeva, who participated in the court session as an accuser, witnessed the power of condemning the criminal. Since then, the desire to be like Tajikhan, like the steadfast and strict judges sitting at the long table, was burning in Khadija's heart.

In 1931, after graduating from the Russian school, Khadija boldly pursued the goal of becoming a lawyer, and entered the preparatory course of the Institute of Soviet Construction and Scientific Research of Law. After studying there for a year, he continued his studies in the second year of the Faculty of Law at the Jahan Obidova Institute of Soviet Construction and Law, which had just been established in Tashkent. During her student years, Khadicha Sulaymanova did not limit herself to reading educational materials, but read every book on the science of law over and over again. Khadija had chosen to become a specialist in criminal law from the legal fields. For that time, this was considered a great courage for a woman. Khadija's student years were very intense.

After graduating from the institute, Khadicha Sulaymanova started working as a people's judge. At the end of 1935, he was elected to the Supreme Court of the Republic. At the age of twenty-two, he was probably one of the first among men and women to receive such a high level of trust. He managed criminal court proceedings in a difficult place.

He served in the Supreme Court for more than three years. During this period, along with enriching his experience, he also increased his theoretical knowledge.

He never stopped learning. In September 1938, he entered the Department of Soviet Criminal Law of the Moscow Law Institute as a graduate student. He had to stop his scientific work for a while due to the beginning of the homeland war. After the end of the war, he defended his dissertation in July 1945 and returned to Tashkent as a candidate of legal sciences. She was the first Uzbek woman to receive a scientific degree in the field of law. In September of this year, Khadicha Sulaymanova was appointed head of the Department of Criminal Law of the Tashkent State Legal Institute. By 1950, he completed his doctoral studies at the SSR Academy of Sciences and defended his doctoral thesis. This case was a big event in the development of the science of jurisprudence in Uzbekistan. In September 1954, he was the director of the Tashkent State Legal Institute, and after the institution was

completed in July 1955, he worked as a dean and headed the department of criminal law when the Faculty of Law was opened at SAGU. Earlier, Khadicha Sulaymanova received the honorary title of "Honored Scientist of the Uzbek SSR". In October 1956, he was elected a full member of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR. This was the fruit of his great services in the development of the country science. From September of this year, he began to perform the duties of the Minister of Justice of the Republic. Khadicha Sulaymanova has done a lot of important work during her career as a minister. These include the development of laws, amendments to the codes, courts, notary and advocacy activities.

One of his most important works is his contribution to the establishment of the Tashkent Scientific Research Institute of Judicial Expertise on January 24, 1958. Currently, this institute is managed by the name of Khadicha Sulaymanova.

He was a brave son of Uzbek, who fought against injustices and was thirsty for knowledge. In April 1964, Khadichha Sulaymanova was elected as the chairman of the Supreme Court of the UZSSR. So far, no woman has been elected to such a position in any country of the world. The interesting thing is that this happiness will be given to an Uzbek girl, not to the women of the USA or European countries, which are considered the homeland of democracy, and it will remain a great historical achievement.

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